

PREDICTORS OF BRAIN DRAIN AND QUALITY OF NURSING CARE IN TERTIARY HEALTHCARE INSTITUTIONS IN CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The healthcare system in Nigeria is increasingly burdened by the exodus of healthcare professionals, particularly nurses, from the country's tertiary healthcare institutions. This research examined Predictors of Brain Drain and Quality of Nursing Care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria. The Push-Pull Theory by Everett Lee (1966) was adopted for the study. It was a cross-sectional study using questionnaires with 308 participants. Population of the study consisted all staffed Nurses in tertiary healthcare institutions in Cross River State with an inclusion rationale that they are Nigerians and must have worked for at least five years. The sample size was 308 respondents. Quantitative data was analyzed using the Population T-test at 0.05 levels of significance via SPSS. Findings showed a statistically significant effect of poor remuneration, workload, and insecurity on quality of Nursing care. It revealed that poor remuneration, workload and insecurity were determinants of Nurses brain drain which negatively affects the quality of nursing care delivery in the University of Calabar Teaching hospital (UCTH) and Federal Neuro-Psychiatry Hospital Calabar (FNPH). Conclusion was drawn that dependable and a well coordinated predictors of brain drain in terms of remuneration, workload and security are very imperative to enhance quality of Nursing care delivery in tertiary health care institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria. It is recommended among others that the government should increase the salaries and wages of Nurses in the

tertiary healthcare institutions as a way to curb brain drain and boosts the quality of Nursing care delivery. (Word Count, 245).

Key Words: Predictors of Brain Drain, Quality of Nursing Care, Tertiary Healthcare Institutions

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, healthcare systems are under enormous pressure because there simply are not enough skilled professionals to meet the growing demand for care. One major reason for this is brain drain. The term brain drain first appeared in the 1960s, introduced by the British Royal Society to describe the migration of scientists and technologists from post-war Europe to North America (Qadri, 2018). It is the migration of healthcare workers from their home countries to overseas (WHO, 2022). The World Health Organization (2022) estimates that there is a shortage of about 5.9 million nurses worldwide, with low and middle-income countries (LMICs) carrying the heaviest burden. The problem is compounded by the constant migration of nurses from their home countries to more developed nations, where they are offered better pay, safer workplaces, and greater chances to advance their careers (International Council of Nurses [ICN], 2022). This kind of migration has serious consequences for the countries nurses they leave in home country, as it strips their health systems of much-needed professional health care workers. The situation is especially severe in the Sub-Saharan African region, which has just 3% of the world's health workforce yet faces 25% of the global disease burden (WHO, 2022). Nigeria is widely acknowledged to have been greatly affected by the migration of nurses; creating critical shortages in the health workforce and making it harder to provide quality nursing care delivery (Akinyemi & Adesanya, 2020). The country is one of the world's top sources of nurse migration, with thousands moving to countries like the United Kingdom, Canada, and Saudi Arabia in search of better opportunities (Nwozichi et al., 2020). Many Nurses in public healthcare facilities complain that their salaries do not reflect the heavy workload they carry, their qualifications, or the rising cost of living. Nurses also complain that sometimes they face harassment, theft, or even physical assault from patients' relatives or criminal elements, especially in hospitals with weak security measures. This seems to create stress, increase burnout, and leaves many feeling abandoned by hospital management and government, influencing their decision to leave. Worthy of note is that, with too few nurses and little workforce planning, many are left caring for more patients than is safe. The WHO recommends a nurse-to-patient ratio of 1:4 in sensitive healthcare settings, yet in many Nigerian tertiary hospitals particularly in urban public institutions ratios can climb to 1:15 or more (WHO, 2022). This may not only strain nurses physically and mentally but also affects the quality of care provided (Ekpenyong et al., 2018). In Cross River State, the situation is much the same. Hospitals such as the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital and the Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital, Calabar, tend to struggle with high staff turnover, low pay, security risks, and irresistible workloads. The loss of experienced nurses, coupled with low morale among those who remain, has led to a noticeable drop in the quality of care (Oyedele, 2021). Despite several government efforts and policy reforms, the migration of nurses and declining standards of care remain serious issues. These realities inspired this study, which seeks to identify the

main predictors of brain drain and examine how they impact the quality of nursing care in tertiary healthcare institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria's healthcare system is facing a growing crisis as more nurses and other health professionals leave the country's tertiary hospitals in search of better opportunities abroad. This wave of migration, often called brain drain, is steadily reducing the number of skilled hands available and, as a result, affecting the quality-of-care patients receive. Tertiary healthcare institutions designed to handle complex cases and provide specialized referral services are among the worst hit. Many struggle to keep their most experienced nurses, with poor working conditions frequently cited as a major reason for their departure (Nwozichi et al., 2020). In Cross River State, the picture is no different. Major institutions such as the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital and the Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital Calabar have seen an alarming increase in nurse turnover. Poor pay, unsafe working environments, and overwhelming workloads have made it increasingly difficult to keep staff motivated. For many nurses, salaries fail to reflect their qualifications, responsibilities, or the rising cost of living, leading them to seek better-paying opportunities abroad or in the private sector. Workplace insecurity ranging from verbal and physical abuse by patients or their relatives to inadequate institutional protection further diminishes morale. This situation has reached such a critical stage that on August 1, 2025, nurses across Nigeria embarked on a nationwide strike to protest over working conditions. Available statistics (about 5.9 million shortages of nurses worldwide, with low and middle-income countries carrying the heaviest burden) reinforce the urgency of the issue (WHO, 2022). As far back as 2018, European countries such as Germany, Hungary, Finland, Italy, and Spain recorded significant increases in visa applications from Nigerian healthcare workers (The Guardian, 2019). These trends raise pressing questions: What is fuelling the migration of Nigerian nurses? And how can this outflow be curtailed without compromising the quality of nursing care in tertiary institutions, particularly in Cross River State? Although the government has introduced measures like salary increments, improved allowances, and other benefits, these efforts have not slowed the migration trend. It is based on this backdrop, that the investigation is thus motivated on the predictors of brain drain and quality of Nursing care in tertiary healthcare institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria to bridge the gap.

Research questions

The following research questions are raised to guide the study:

How does poor remuneration affect the quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State

To what extent does workload affect the quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State.

How does insecurity affect the quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study was to examine the predictors of brain drain and quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

assess the effect of poor remuneration on quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

determine the effect of workload on quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

examine the effect of insecurity on quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were used for the study.

There is no statistically significant effect of poor remuneration on quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

There is no statistically significant effect of workload on quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

There is no statistically significant effect of insecurity on quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Poor Remuneration and Quality of Nursing Care

Adebayo and Olamide (2020) examined nurses working in three tertiary hospitals in South-West Nigeria and found a clear, statistically significant association between pay satisfaction and the quality of nursing care. Their findings showed that nurses who felt underpaid often had lower morale, reduced dedication to their duties, and were more prone to lapses in patient care. They concluded that dissatisfaction with remuneration could reduce attentiveness, ultimately harming patient outcomes. In a similar vein, Nwozichi et al. (2020) conducted a cross-sectional survey in selected Nigerian hospitals and reported that 68% of nurses dissatisfied with their salaries also admitted to spending less time and effort on patient care. The study linked inadequate pay to higher job-related stress and lower efficiency, which in turn compromised service quality. Likewise, a study conducted in Jordan by Khatatbeh et al. (2021) found that nurses who perceived their salaries as insufficient were more likely to deliver substandard care due to low motivation and increased psychological strain. Echoing these perspectives, the International Council of Nurses (ICN, 2022) stresses that fair and competitive wages are vital for sustaining nursing care standards and ensuring patient safety.

Workload and Quality of Nursing Care

Aiken et al. (2017), in a landmark investigation spanning 12 European countries, identified a clear negative link between nurses' workloads and the quality of patient care. Their analysis revealed that with each additional patient assigned to a nurse, the likelihood of patient mortality increased by 7%. The authors emphasized that lowering workloads is essential to safeguarding patient safety and optimizing nursing performance. Ekpenyong et al. (2018) assessed nurses working in tertiary hospitals in the southern region and found that over 60% were dissatisfied with their working conditions, primarily due to heavy patient loads and inadequate staffing.

Many nurses reported experiencing fatigue, reduced concentration, and a noticeable decline in care quality. Also, Ojo and Olatunji (2020), in a cross-sectional study involving three teaching hospitals, found that excessive workloads contributed to higher levels of job dissatisfaction, burnout, and lapses in patient monitoring.

Insecurity and Quality of Nursing Care

Hassankhani et al. (2018), in a cross-sectional study in Iran, observed that nurses who faced physical assaults or threats from patients and their relatives often experienced emotional burnout, which weakened their capacity to deliver quality care. The study highlighted that unsafe work settings contribute to increased stress, low staff morale, and a stronger desire among nurses to leave the job. Okafor and Okocha (2019) in their study examined how workplace violence affects the quality of care in public hospitals. They found that 62% of nurses had been victims of at least one violent incident in the previous year, with many linking these experiences to the absence of adequate security staff and poor management responses to safety breaches. The researchers concluded that such conditions reduce nurses' motivation and make it harder for them to fully attend to patients' needs. George et al. (2020) on the other hand reported from tertiary hospitals in South-East Nigeria that insecurity ranging from fears of attacks by patients' relatives to poorly lit wards and the lack of emergency response procedures significantly predicted lower standards of patient care.

Theoretical framework

The Push-Pull Theory

The proponent of the Push-Pull theory is Everett lee (1966). The Push-Pull theory of migration holds that people migrate because of a combination of factors that push them away from their place of origin and pull them toward a new destination. According to the Push-Pull theory, factors that causes people to migrate to other destinations included and not limited to unemployment, poverty, political instability, natural disasters, conflict, lack of services, poor remuneration, workload insecurity etc as push factors while, job opportunities, better living conditions, political stability, access to services and safety as pull factors. The implication of the Push-Pull theory to the study is that Nurses brain drain in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State may be as a result of the Push-factors such as poor remuneration, workload, insecurity among others and the Pull-factors such as better salaries and wages, job opportunities, safety, less work and political stability. To Push-pull theory, these factors play significant role in migration of healthcare professionals especially staffed Nurses to different countries thereby affecting the quality of Nursing care in tertiary healthcare institutions of their home country, Nigeria and Cross River State in Particular. The push-pull theory is relevant to the study in its explanations of the factors that predicts brain drain among nurses in tertiary healthcare institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study adopted the cross-sectional research design. This was because the design was concerned with the study of large and small populations with emphasis on the incidence, distribution and interrelations of sociological and psychological factors. The area of this study was Calabar Cross River State, Nigeria. Population of the study comprised of all staffed Nurses

both male and female with an inclusion rationale that they are Nigerians and must have worked in the tertiary health care institutions for at least five (5) years in Cross River State, Nigeria. The sample size for this study was 308 respondents. This was made up of staff Nurses in the tertiary healthcare institutions in the study area. Since, the total population of staff Nurses who are Nigerians and have worked for at least five (5) years in the tertiary healthcare institutions in Cross River state was infinite due to Japa syndrome, the researcher used estimated population figure to get the sample size 308 respondents for the study. The Kish Leslie (1965) formula for cross sectional studies was used to determine the sample size for an estimated population. The sampling techniques adopted for this study were the simple random sampling techniques and purposive sampling techniques. The simple random sampling technique was used in the selection of two tertiary healthcare facilities out of the three in Cross River State. These randomly selected tertiary healthcare facilities were the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UCTH) and the Federal Neuro-Psychiatry hospital Calabar (FNPH). To achieve this, names of the three tertiary hospitals were written on a sheet of paper wrapped and put in a container, and then a neutral person (research assistant) was asked to select without replacement until the desired number of two tertiary health care facilities (UCTH & FNPH Calabar) were selected for the study. The process (draws) was done twice. This was done in order to give every research subject the equal chance of being selected into the sample. The simple random sampling method was relevant to this study because it is devoid of biases. The purposive sampling technique was used to select the number of Nurses from each of the two randomly selected tertiary healthcare facilities who were qualified to fill the research instruments. The researcher purposively selected 308 Nurses from the two randomly selected tertiary healthcare facilities (UCTH & FNPH) Calabar, Cross River State. This was done as follows; the researcher purposively selected 208 Nurses from the UCTH Calabar and 100 Nurses from the FNPH Calabar respectively. The purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling method that gave the researcher opportunity to select his subjects based on his discretion and purpose of the study such as population size, location and vulnerability. The questionnaire was instrument for data collection. It was structured to reflect the four point likert-scale type of strongly agree, agree, strongly disagreed and disagreed accordingly. It was subjected to both face and content validity. To determine the reliability of the instrument a pilot test was conducted. This was obtained through the Cronbach's Alpha reliability method. The population Test was used for the analysis of data carried out at 0.05 levels of significance. All the 308 questionnaires were properly filled and returned to the researcher for analysis and discussions of findings

Results

Table 1 Responses to poor remuneration and quality of Nursing care

S/NO.	Statement	Variables	Frequency	Percent (%)
1	You will prefer to work abroad because of the attractive salaries and wages	SA	227	26.3
		A	81	73.7

		SD	-	-
		D	-	-
			308	100
	Total			
2	You will like to work of better transportation allowances	SA	249	80.8
		A	59	19.2
		SD	-	-
		D	-	-
	Total		308	100
3	Better disengagement/severance packages is the reason you to want to work abroad	SA	270	87.7
		A	38	12.3
		SD	-	-
		D	-	-
	Total		308	100
4	Your desire to leave your country for better pay packages affect your ability to provide adequate patients care	SA	165	53.6
		A	124	40.3
		SD	-	-
		D	19	6.2
		A	124	40.3
	Total		308	100

Source: Field Work 2025

Table 1 showed responses to poor remuneration and quality of Nursing car. It revealed that out of the 308 questionnaires retrieved, 227(73.7 %) of the respondents strongly agreed that they will prefer to work abroad because of the attractive salaries and wages, 81(26.3%) of the respondents agreed, while strongly disagreed and disagreed had no response. Also, 249(80.8%) respondents strongly agreed that they will like to work of better transportation allowances, 59(19.2%) respondents agreed.

270(87.7%)of the respondents strongly agreed that Better disengagement/severance package is the reason they will want to work abroad, 38(12.3%) of the respondents agreed, In addition, 165(53.6%) respondents strongly agreed that they desire to leave your country for better pay packages, 124(40.3 %) of the respondents agreed, while 19(6.2%) respondents strongly disagreed.

Table 2 (a & b) Summary of Population T-test calculation of the effects of poor remuneration on quality of Nursing care

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Poor remuneration	308	2.9400	1.16965	.12696
Quality of Nursing care	308	2.9500	1.25918	.12092

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Poor remuneration	25.581	306	.000	2.95000	2.3179	3.1721
Quality of Nursing care	26.397	306	.000	2.96000	2.7101	3.1799

Significant at *P<.05; critical t-value: 1.98, d.f; 306

Source: Field Work 2025

Result of analysis in table 2 (a & b) showed the test result from the population T-Test (t). The calculated r-values 25.581 + 26.397, is greater than critical t-value 1.98 at 0.05 levels of significance with 306 degrees of freedom. This guarantees the rejection of the (H0) null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a statistically significant effect of poor remuneration on quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Table 3 Responses to workload and quality of Nursing care

S/NO.	Statement	Variables	Frequency	Percent (%)
1	You handle so many medical cases when you are on duty	SA	224	72.7
		A	81	26.3
		SD	-	-
		D	3	1.0
		Total	308	100
2	If you had opportunity to leave the country, you will leave due to the workload in the health care facilities	SA	243	78.9
		A	62	20.1
		SD	-	-
		D	3	1.0
		Total	308	100

3	The quality of nursing care by staffed Nurses in UCTH and FNPH is affected as a result of the workload in the health care facilities	SA	264	85.7
		A	41	13.3
		SD	-	-
		D	3	1.0
	Total		308	100
4	Due to brain drain, some patients are abandoned by nurses in the tertiary healthcare institutions	SA	159	51.6
		A	127	41.2
		SD	3	1.0
		D	19	6.2
			308	100

Source: Field Work 2025

Table 3 showed responses to workload and quality of Nursing care. It showed that from the 308 questionnaires retrieved, 224(72.7%) of respondents strongly agreed that they handle so many medical cases when you are on duty, 81(26.3%) of respondents agreed, while 3(1.0) of the respondents disagreed. Also, 243(78.9%) of the respondents strongly agreed that If you had opportunity to leave the country, you will leave due to the workload in the health care facilities, 62(20.1%) of the respondents agreed, while 3(1.0) of the respondents disagreed. 264(85.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed that the quality of nursing care by staffed Nurses in UCTH and FNPH is affected as a result of the workload in the health care facilities 41(13.3%) respondents agreed, while 3(1.0) respondents disagreed. In addition, 159(51.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Due to brain drain, some patients are abandoned by nurses in the tertiary healthcare institutions, 127(41.2 %) which constituted a high proportion of the respondents agreed while 3(1.0) of the respondents disagreed and 19(6.2%) of the respondents strongly disagreed,

Table 4(a & b) Summary of Population T-test calculation of the effects of workload on quality of Nursing care

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Workload	308	3.220	1.24137	.12414
Quality of Nursing care	308	2.950	1.24150	.12415

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0						
	T	f	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Workload	24.533		306	.000	3.12000	2.77	3.3662
Quality of Nursing care	24.505		306	.000	2.90000	2.67	3.1565

Source: Field Work, 2025

Result of analysis in table 4 (a & b) showed the test result from the population T-Test (t). The calculated r-values 24.533 + 24.505, is greater than critical t-value 1.98 at 0.05 levels of significance with 306 degrees of freedom. This guarantees the rejection of the (H0) null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis which states that there is no statistically significant effect of workload on quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Table 5 Responses to insecurity and quality of Nursing care

S/NO.	Statement	Variables	Frequency	Percent (%)
1	The fear of insecurity affect the quality of nursing care in health facilities	SA	227	73.7
		A	78	25.3
		SD	-	-
		D	3	1.0
		Total	308	100
2	Nurses brain drain is caused by the fear of being beaten by patients	SA	246	79.9
		A	59	19.2
		SD	-	-
		D	3	1.0
		Total	308	100
3	Patients abandonment by nurses is because of abuse, physical assault, threats from patients' relatives	SA	264	85.7
		A	38	12.3
		SD	-	-
		D	6	1.9
		Total	308	100

			308	100
4	Job security plays a significant role in retaining Staffed Nurses and sustaining quality of patients care	SA	159	51.6
		A	124	40.3
		SD	-	-
		D	25	1.9
			308	100

Source: Field Work 2025

Table 5 showed responses to insecurity and quality of Nursing care. It showed that out of the 308 questionnaires retrieved 227(73.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed that the fear of insecurity affect the quality of nursing care in health facilities 78(25.25.3%) of the respondents agreed, while 3(1.0) of the respondents disagreed. Also showed that 246(79.9%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Nurses brain drain is caused by the fear of being beaten by patients, 59(19.2%) of the respondents agreed, while 3(1.0) of the respondents disagreed. In addition, 264(85.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed that patients abandonment by nurses is because of Patients abandonment by nurses is because of abuse, physical assault, threats from patients’ relatives 38(12.3%) of the respondents agreed, while 6(1.9%) of the respondents disagreed. Also, 159(51.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that job security plays a significant role in retaining staffed Nurses and sustaining quality of patients care, 124(40.3 %) respondents agreed while 25(1.9%) of the respondents disagreed.

Table 5 (a & b) Summary of Population T-test calculation of the effects of insecurity on quality of Nursing care

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Insecurity	308	2.700	1.15764	.11676
Quality of Nursing care	308	2.530	1.25078	.10558

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Insecurity	23.548	306	.000	3.030	2.6624	3.1376
Quality of Nursing care	23.487	306	.000	3.130	2.5215	3.1385

Source: Field Work, 2024

Result of analysis in table 5 (a & b) showed the test result from the population T-Test (t) on effects of insecurity on quality of Nursing care. The calculated t-values 23.548 + 23.487, is greater than critical t-value 1.98 at 0.05 levels of significance with 306 degrees of freedom. This guarantees the rejection of the (H₀) null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a statistically significant effect of insecurity on quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Discussions

Result of hypothesis 1 revealed that there is a statistically significant effect of poor remuneration on quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria. This implies that poor remuneration as a predictor of brain drain affects the quality of nursing care delivery in tertiary health care institutions (University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UCTH) & Federal Neuro-Psychiatry Hospital Calabar (FNPH) in Cross River State, Nigeria. The finding is in line with Adebayo and Olamide (2020) and Nwozichi et al. (2020). Adebayo and Olamide (2020) study revealed that Nurses who were poorly paid reported low morale, decreased job commitment, and greater incidence of negligence in patient care. Nwozichi et al. (2020) found that 68% of nurses who reported dissatisfaction with their salaries also reported a decline in the time and effort they devoted to patient care. The study linked poor remuneration to increased job stress and reduced efficiency, ultimately compromising care quality. The case is not different with the tertiary healthcare institutions particularly the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UCTH) and the Federal Neuro-Psychiatry Hospital Calabar (FNPH) in Cross River State, Nigeria, considering the current economic situation amidst oil subsidy removal. It was also observed that Nurses prefer to work abroad because of the attractive salaries and wages hence the reason for brain drain or Jap syndrome.

Result of hypothesis 2 also revealed that there is a statistically significant effect of workload on quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions (University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UCTH) and the Federal Neuro-Psychiatry hospital Calabar (FNPH) in Cross River State, Nigeria. This means that workload as a predictor of brain drain affects the quality of Nursing care delivery in tertiary healthcare institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria. The findings tallied with that of Aiken et al. (2017) and Ekpenyong et al. (2018). Aiken et al. (2017) study revealed that for every additional patient assigned to a nurse, the risk of patient mortality increased by 7 percent and that reducing workload was essential to improving both patient safety and nursing performance. Ekpenyong et al. (2018) findings revealed that over 60% of nurses were dissatisfied with their working conditions due to excessive patient loads and inadequate staffing and that Nurses reported fatigue, reduced concentration, and a decline in the quality of care provided. This study also observed that Nurses will want to leave their country (Nigeria) if they had opportunity to leave, due to the workload in the health care facilities. This is an indication that workload is a predictor of brain drain (Japa syndrome) hence affecting the quality of Nursing care in tertiary healthcare institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Result of hypothesis 3 revealed that there is a statistically significant effect of insecurity on quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria. By implication it means that insecurity as a predictor of brain drain affects the quality of quality of Nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State. The findings agrees with

that of Hassankhani et al. (2018) and Okafor and Okocha (2019). Hassankhani et al. (2018) investigations revealed that nurses exposed to physical violence and threats from patients or their relatives experienced emotional exhaustion, that which negatively impacted their ability to deliver high-quality patient care. Okafor and Okocha (2019) study revealed that 62% of nurses had experienced at least one form of violence in the past year, with a significant portion attributing it to lack of security personnel and poor administrative response to safety incidents and that workplace insecurity diminished nurses' motivation and their capacity to focus on patients' needs. It was also observed that patient's abandonment by nurses is because of abuse, physical assault, threats from patients' relatives in tertiary health care facilities in Cross River State, Nigeria. It can also be concluded that Nurses brain drain (Japa syndrome) is because of the fear of the insecurity in the tertiary health care facilities.

Conclusion

The study on predictors of brain drain and quality of nursing care in Tertiary Healthcare Institutions in Cross River State, Nigeria revealed that poor remuneration, workload and insecurity were determinants of Nurses brain drain (Japa syndrome) which negatively affects the quality of nursing care delivery in University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UCTH) and the Federal Neuro-Psychiatry Hospital (FNPH) Calabar Cross River State Nigeria.. It was noted that Brain drain in Nigeria disproportionately benefit the healthcare professionals especially staff Nurses amidst the present socio-economic situation and place a heavy risk on the patients, healthcare institutions, government budget, diverting human resources from home country to other nations of the world. The study highlights the vital role of Nurses in healthcare service delivery in the provision of patients care in the tertiary healthcare institutions in Cross River State. In view of the research results, conclusion was drawn that dependable and a well coordinated predictors of brain drain in terms of remuneration, workload and security are very imperative to enhance quality of Nursing care delivery in tertiary health care institutions in the study area. The study helps inform healthcare policies and intervention on brain drain to ensure retention, safer health practices and improve the quality of Nursing care in Nigeria particularly in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made.

The government should as a matter of urgency increase the salaries and wages of Nurses in the tertiary healthcare institutions. One of the main reasons health workers leave is because they feel their efforts are not valued financially. To keep them, salaries need to be more attractive and consistent with what professionals earn elsewhere in Africa. Beyond just money, incentives like housing support, transport allowances, and health insurance for their families can make them feel appreciated. This will go a long way to reduce the number of Nurses migration to other countries for higher pay and boosts the quality of Nursing care delivery.

The nurses-patients ratio should be urgently reviewed. Many doctors and nurses in Cross River's tertiary institutions are overworked because there are simply not enough hands to share the job. This often leads to burnout and frustration. Recruiting more staff, creating fair work shifts, and ensuring that healthcare workers have time to rest and spend with their families can

go a long way. Hospitals should also be equipped with modern tools and systems, like electronic health records and telemedicine, to reduce the stress of manual tasks

The government should provide armed security operatives to protect Nurses on duty in the healthcare facilities. Protecting hospital premises with better lighting, surveillance cameras, and trained security personnel is essential. Government should also make it a priority to provide safe transportation and staff quarters, especially for those on night duty. Knowing that their lives are valued and protected can make healthcare workers more confident about staying.

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